

DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATIC ELECTRIC FAN

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop an automatic electric fan using a microcontroller, PIR sensor, DHT22 sensor, relays and LCD. An experimental design was employed to evaluate the performance of the system in terms of automatic switching on/off, automatic changing in speed level, automatic temperature and relative humidity monitoring, effective distance and sensitive time of detection of the system. Findings revealed that the electric fan automatically turned on/off when the user is detected and not detected, respectively, the speed level of the electric fan changes with respect to the speed level thresholds using various simulations, and the system successfully monitored the ambient temperature of the room. Another finding revealed that the minimum effective detection distance of the sensor is around one meter with a corresponding time sensitivity of 1.4 seconds, and the maximum effective distance is around six meters with a corresponding time sensitivity of 4.2 seconds. The longer the distance of the user from the sensor, the longer it takes also to be detected. Thus, the study performed a more convenient to users as the electric fan don't need a manual intervention with additional feature of real-time temperature monitoring.

Keywords: Arduino Uno, automation, DHT22, PIR, speed level, temperature monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

Automation outgrew and takes up of great advantages to the people where everything works without the intervention of the manual operation. People today were confined in their houses resulting to the unpredicted ambience temperature outside caused by the climate change. The urbanization contributes to the significant effects in the temperature trends (Estoque et al., 2020, Sidika, 2018), which may result to possible health-related risks in the Philippine (Manalo et al., 2021, Estoque et al., 2020). Likewise, the Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA) published that heat cramps and heat exhaustion are the possible in human body when exposing with the

temperatures ranging from 32°C to 41°C and too much exposure will cause heat stroke.

Nowadays, many rely on the cooling machines, like electric fans or air conditioning units but mostly choose electric fan (Talib et al., 2020, Kanchanasatian, 2018, NSO & DOE, 2011) because it is more affordable, portable in some cases and less energy consumption (NSO & DOE, 2011), even in the University of Eastern Philippines, specifically in the College of Engineering, each classroom is being installed with ceiling fans or wall fans (Ampuan et al. 2019). These fans operate every day to sustain comfortable class activities and make the room more conducive for learning. One of the problems is the negligence on the utilization of these fans as users tend to forget to turn them off (Talib et al., 2020, Sidika, 2018,

Kanchanasatian, 2018), which may result overheating to the fan as it operates in the evening without users and will cause fire when the motor gets heated up. Last problem is the inconvenience of the users, specifically the students and faculty members, in manual turning on/off, and increase and decreasing of the fan (Pujaria et al., 2020, Talib et al., 2019, Ampuan et al, 2019, Kanchanasatian, 2018).

To aid such concerns, this study aimed to develop an automatic electric fans controlled by a programmable Arduino Uno Board in a specified room which automatically turn on/off when the user enters/leaves the room using PIR sensor which detects the presence of the users, and the fans will automatically change the speed of the fan with respect to the ambient temperature of the room using LM35 Sensor. This study is a development of the author's undergraduate thesis which failed to meet a more accurate temperature sensor as the previous study acquired LM35 sensor, lacking of indicators on the system and risky circuit of the components (Bless Ampuan et al, 2019). This development is designed to measure a more precise temperature reading using DHT22 which measured not only temperature reading but also relative humidity, installed LCD for visualization as to monitor directly the variables needed to measure or detect by the sensors, and a safer circuitry using power supply and buck converter.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Design Concept. The block diagram of the system was employed as shown in Figure 1. The inputs are motion sensor and relative humidity and temperature sensor. The controller, Arduino Uno Board, process and control the sensors and relay switch. Once the PIR sensor detect the user, the PIR motion sensor will send digital signals to the controller and it will process the received data, and send signals to the relay module to activate the electric fan.

Figure 1. Block Diagram of the System

The circuit diagram of the system is shown in Figure 2. The system is powered by 230AC source. The relay module (6) is connected to the ac source and interconnects the controller (2) and electric fan (7). The controller (2) is powered by the 12V Power Supply (1) which is

connected from the AC source and converts the 12V DC into 5V using buck converter (5). The controller interconnects the DHT22 relative humidity and temperature sensor (4), PIR sensor (3), relay module (6), LCD (8) and LED indicators (9). The electric fan (7) is connected from the 230 AC source and controlled by the controller through the relay module (6).

Figure 2. Circuit Diagram of the System

Microcontroller. This is a programmable small controller, which process and control the sensors and relay. This will receive digital signals from the sensors and send signal to the relay to activate the Electric Fan (Talib et al., 2020, Ampuan et al., 2019, Sidika, 2018).

Electric Fan. This study acquired the 230V capacity electric fan considering the availability in the area. It has three speed levels, level 1, level 2 and level 3.

Motion sensor. This sensor used to detect the movement of human being in a form of emitted infrared heat, this sends signals to the microcontroller Arduino Uno Board to trigger the system, this is attained using the PIR motion sensor (Talib et al, 2020, Ampuan et al, 2019, Kanchanasatian, 2018).

Relative Humidity and Temperature sensor. This sensor used to measure the relative humidity and ambient temperature of the room. This study acquired the temperature parameters This will be used to automatically adjust the speed of the fan, dependent on the ambient temperature. This is attained using the DHT22 sensor. This type is sensor is being used nowadays in smart home automations (Pujaria et al., 2020, Kanchanasatian, 2018).

Power Supply. This is a 12V DC output power supply which is connected from the 230V AC source, which supplied current to the buck converter and relay module.

Relay module. This is used to electronically open or close the circuit to activate or deactivate the electric fan, respectively.

Buck Converter

This is used to convert 12V DC to 5V to supply current in the Arduino Uno board.

Liquid Crystal Display. A 16x2 LCD is used to display the temperature value, speed level of the fan and motion detected of the system.

Light Emitting Diode. Three (3) LEDs were used which served as the indicators for level 1, 2 and 3 speed of the fan.

Performance Test

Effective Distance of Detection. The sensor is designed to detect a person with a maximum sensing range of 7m based on its product specification. The researcher tested its sensing range by having 8 distances from the sensors such as 1m, 2m, 3m, 4m, 5, 6m, 7m and 8m using a measuring tape.

Sensitive Time of Detection. The researcher measured the time sensitivity of detection using a timer which corresponds to the effective distance of detection in 8 distances from the sensors such as 1m, 2m, 3m, 4m, 5, 6m, 7m and 8m.

Automatic Switching On/Off. The automated switching on/off system was tested in three cases. The first case is when the users enters in the field of view of the PIR sensor, the second case is when the users sitting and staying in the chairs within the field of view and the latter case is when the students leaving the room.

Automatic Speed Regulation. The automated speed regulation of the system was tested through simulations by using the cooling equipment and heating equipment to control the temperature to increase and decrease the speed of the fan. The first case simulated the temperature until it reached the speed level 1 threshold of the fan, the second case is simulated to reach the speed level 2 of the fan, and the speed level 3 is simulated to reach the speed level 3 of the fan. The speed level 1 threshold is from 24°C to 25°C, the speed level 2 is from 26°C to 28°C and the speed level 3 is above 29°C.

Automatic Temperature Monitoring. Ambient Temperature was monitored remotely through the LCD every hour duration.

III. RESULTS

Effective Distance

The effective distance of the sensor to detect the users is 6m as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Effective Distance of Detection

Distance	Fan Output
1m	Turned On
2m	Turned On
3m	Turned On
4m	Turned On
5m	Turned On
6m	Tuned On
7m	Turned Off
8m	Turned Off

Sensitivity of the system

The sensitivity of the system to detect the users is 1.4s and 4.1s as minimum time sensitivity and maximum time sensitivity for the 1m minimum effective distance and 6m maximum effective distance, respectively, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Time Sensitivity of Detection

Distance	Time detected (s)
1m	1.4s
2m	1.9s
3m	2.4
4m	3.1
5m	3.8
6m	4.2s
7m	Not detected
8m	Not detected

The performance of the automatic electric fan in terms of automatic switching on/off is revealed in Table 2. The fan automatically turned on in case 1 and case 2, but automatically turned off in case 3. Similar findings on the study of Talib et al. (2020), Ampuan et al. (2019), and Sadiki (2019).

Table 3. Results of the Automatic Switching On/Off of the Electric Fan

Case	Fan Output
1	Turned On
2	Turned On
3	Turned Off

Automatic Speed Regulation Performance

The performance of the automatic electric fan in terms of automatic speed regulation is revealed in Table 3. The fan automatically changes its speed with respect to its target temperature thresholds.

Table 4. Results of the Automatic Switching On/Off of the Electric Fan

Case	Fan Output
1	Turned on at Speed Level 1
2	Turned on at Speed Level 2
3	Turned on at Speed Level 3

Automatic Temperature Monitoring.

The researcher used the LCD of the system to monitor the temperature from 8:00Am to 5:00Pm. Furthermore, the researcher conducted a 7-day Actual Ambient Temperature reading.

The line graphs in Figure 3 showed the room ambient temperature reading with respect to the time it was measured every hour at the University of Eastern Philippines. Thus, the result come up that the lowest temperature attained inside the room was 26-28 degrees Celsius and the highest was 30-31 degrees Celsius.

Figure 3. Actual Temperature Reading in LCD from January 16-22, 2022

IV. DISCUSSION

The effective distance of the sensor is 6m as shown in Table 1. Hence, the system is

designed to detect users at maximum 6m from the sensor. The functionality of the first feature of the automated fans in terms of the automatic switching on/off is working properly. As the users entered within the sensing range of the sensor, the fan automatically turn on and while the users are staying, the fan still operates and when they leave the room, after the time delay, the fan automatically turned off. The LCD displayed “User detected” when the user is within the sensing range of the system, and “The system will shut down in 3 seconds” will be displayed when there are no users in the area. Moreover, the second feature of the system which is the automatic speed regulation worked properly. As the temperature reached within the temperature threshold 24°C to 25°C, the LED indicator for Speed Level 1 turned on and the measured ambient temperature is reflected in the LCD. As the temperature reached within the temperature threshold 26°C to 28°C, the LED indicator for Speed Level 2 turned on and the measured ambient temperature is reflected in the LCD. As the temperature reached above 29°C, the LED indicator for Speed Level 3 turned on and the measured ambient temperature is reflected in the LCD. The accuracy of the sensor was attained by monitoring remotely the temperature using the LCD.

V. CONCLUSION

This study developed an automatic electric fan with three features: the automatic switching on/off using a PIR sensors, the automatic speed regulation using DHT22 sensors and the automatic temperature monitoring using LCD. Materials such as power supply, buck converter and LEDs were also acquired. The tested maximum effective detection distance of the sensor is around six meters with a corresponding time sensitivity of 4.2 seconds. The tested minimum effective detection distance of the sensor is around one meter with a corresponding time sensitivity of 1.4 seconds. As long as the user is within the sensing range of the PIR sensor, the electric fan will trigger. The higher ambient temperature the higher the speed level of the fan.

The researcher recommends for further study the integration of the Internet of Things on the system for remote monitoring, alarm warning system in case of hazard heat index, and include the heat index in the variables.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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